

SiDMACIB plugin – Static problem: Manual 2019

1 Introduction

The under development SiDMACIB plugin intends to design the structurally-sound masonry interlocking units with non-isotropic sliding behaviour. Interlocking units are rigid blocks which, on their faces, have a number of locks keeping the blocks together and preventing sliding.

This version of SiDMACIB plugin enables the designers to model a single layer assemblage composed of conventional or interlocking blocks and analyse their structural feasibility. The implemented structural analysis is a concave contact model within the limit state framework developed for corrugated interfaces having locks with rectangular cross section. Sliding of such interfaces is constrained by the Coulomb's friction law and by the shear resistance of the locks along two orthogonal directions.

In this manual, the proposed design process is first introduced. Then all the developed GH components for this process are presented.

2 Installing SiDMACIB plugin for grasshopper

Opening Grasshopper within the Rhinoceros 3D, Grasshopper Assembly File “Sidmacib.gha” should be saved in the folder shown in [Figure 1](#).

Figure 1. Installing the plugin

3 Design process

The design process including the modelling and analysis phases is outlined in [Figure 2](#).

Figure 2. Design process outline

4 Modelling Phase

4.1 Outer surface

The outer surface can have an arbitrary shape. Representing the surface grids by U and V axes, $\vec{u} \otimes \vec{v}$ must be outwards. The surface can be closed along v direction (Figure 3) and also be converged towards the surface apex and be closed along u direction (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The plug-in provided also several GH components to model the overall surface with various geometries:

Component	Description
Circular Arch component (CArch)	
Input	
Base Point (BPt)	Mid-point of arch base line
Extrusion Direction (ED)	the direction of the arch extrusion
Radius (R)	Radius of arch
Height (H)	Distance between apex and base point of arch
Depth (D)	Depth of arch
Output	
Circular Arch (CA)	

Component	Description
Freeform Shell (FSH)	Construct a freeform shell by a set of curves
Input	
Curves (Cs)	Curves on shell
Output	

Component	Description
Oval Arch (OArch)	
Input	
Base Point (BPt)	Mid-point of arch base line
Extrusion Direction (ED)	The direction of the arch extrusion
Horizontal Radius (HR)	Horizontal radius of arch
Vertical Radius (VR)	Vertical radius of arch
Height (H)	Distance between apex and base point of arch
Depth (D)	Depth of arch
Output	

Oval Arch (OA)

Component

Description

Pointed Arch (PArch)

Input

Base Point (BPt)

Mid-point of arch base line

Extrusion Direction (ED)

The direction of the arch extrusion

Radius (R)

Radius of arch

Depth (D)

Depth of arch

Smoothness (S)

A value determining smoothness of curve

Output

Pointed Arch (PA)

Component	Description
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Sail Linear Vault (SLVault)

Input

Base Point (BPt)	Mid-point of vault base plane
Mid Height (MH)	Distance between apex and base point of vault
X Arch Height (XAH)	Distance between apex and base point of the arch in x direction
Y Arch Height (YAH)	Distance between apex and base point of the arch in y direction
X Arch Span (XAS)	Span of the arch in x direction
Y Arch Span (YAS)	Span of the arch in y direction
Smoothness (S)	A value determining smoothness of vault

Output

Sail Linear Vault (SLV)

Component	Description
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Sail Radial Vault (SRVault)

Input

Base Point (BPt)	Mid-point of vault base plane
Mid Height (MH)	Distance between apex and base point of vault
X Arch Height (XAH)	Distance between apex and base point of the arch in x direction
Y Arch Height (YAH)	Distance between apex and base point of the arch in y direction
X Arch Span (XAS)	Span of the arch in x direction
Y Arch Span (YAS)	Span of the arch in y direction
Smoothness (S)	A value determining smoothness of vault

KB*

Ratio of the key block base to the vault base

Output

Sail Radial Vault (SRV)

* For an assemblage with radial grid, a key unit is considered on top of the model whose number of faces equals the number of the blocks in *U* direction (Figure 3).

Component	Description
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Spherical Dome (SphDome)

Input

Base Point (BPt)	Mid-point of dome base plane
Radius (R)	Radius of dome
Height (H)	Distance between apex and base point of dome
Key Angle (KA)	The meridian angle α of the key unit

Output

Spherical Dome (SpD)

4.2 Inner surface

Inner surface, same as the outer one, can have an arbitrary shape, while $\vec{u} \otimes \vec{v}$ is outwards. In this version of the plug-in, the designer, during the discretization, must control that the main body of each block has flat faces, manually. Automated face flatness check and/or flattening the curved faces will be regarded in the further versions.

4.3 surface Discretization

Using *Divide Surface* GH component, either of inner and outer surfaces can be discretized to generate stuck bonding pattern. U and V determine numbers of segments in U and V directions (Figure 4). Surfaces must be discretised so that all blocks are hexahedron units with flat faces. The output is a data tree of points representing the block corners of outer interfaces (Figure 5).

The coordinate of the block corners can be changed on the surfaces parametrically, as far as the hexahedron units with flat faces are generated.

It is worth noting that any trees of block corners for the outer and inner surface which produce hexahedron units with flat faces can be assigned by the designer (with no need to model the overall surfaces and discretize them) to model the assemblage.

Figure 4. Discretizing the outer surface using Divide Surface component.

Figure 5. Data tree of block corners of the blocks on the outer/ inner surfaces.

4.4 Block modelling

A GH component is prepared to model the blocks and their centroids. Given the U , V , and W axes for the assemblage, three axes for a hexahedron unit is denoted u , v , and w (Figure 6).

Figure 6. A hexahedron unit and its three main axes.

Given the data tree of the block corners on the outer and inner surfaces, four sets of block faces are generated through GH component BFaces: $uv0$ faces on the outer surface; $uv1$ faces on the inner surface; uw faces; and vw faces (Figure 7a). The data trees of these sets are demonstrated in Figure 7b.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. four sets of block faces and their data trees.

Component	Description
Block Faces and Centroids (BFaces)	
Input	
Layer 0 Points (I0P)	Block corners on the outer surface
Layer 1 Points (I1P)	Block corners on the inner surface
Output	
UV0 Faces (UV0F)	Faces on the outer surface
UV1 Faces (UV1F)	Faces on the inner surface
WU0 Faces (WU0F)*	<i>uw</i> faces
VW0 Faces (VW0F)	<i>vw</i> faces
Block Centroids (BC)	Centroids of blocks

* In the future the plugin enables the designers to model multi-layer assemblages. *uw* and *vw* faces of Layer *i* will be denoted *WUi* and *VWi*.

Layer 0 Points (I0P)	Block corners on the outer surface
Layer 1 Points (I1P)	Block corners on the inner surface
Orientation (O)	Orientation of locks on vw faces
Lock Number (LN)	Number of locks on a vw face
Output	
VW0 Lock Points (VW0LP)	End points of lock centerline on vw faces
VW0 Lock Centre-line (VW0LCL)	Lock centerline on vw faces

5 Analysis phase

5.1 Determining the boundary condition

Given the topology of an assemblage, through the data trees of the block corners on the outer and inner surfaces, a GH component determines the index of faces which can be chosen as the supports. For the i^{th} face on the m^{th} branch of a data tree of each of four groups of faces, when each branch has n faces, the face index is $(m+1)n + i$.

Every uv_0 and uv_1 interface can be selected as a support. The designer can also select the uw and vw interfaces located on the outer edge of the shell as supports.

Component	Description
Potential Supports (PSupports)	
Input	
Layer 0 Points (I0P)	Block corners on the outer surface
Layer 1 Points (I1P)	Block corners on the inner surface
Output	
Layer 0 UV PSupports (UVPS0)	Index of uv potential supports on the outer surface
Layer 1 UV PSupports (UVPS1)	Index of uv potential supports on the inner surface
Layer 0 WU PSupports (WUPS0)	Index of uw potential supports on the outer surface
Layer 0 VW PSupports (VWPS0)	Index of vw potential supports on the outer surface

5.2 Loading

An external force and an external torque with arbitrary values and directions can be imposed to the centroid of each block. Either of them is defined by a 3D vector. The block centroids stored in a data tree (Section 4.4) are flattened as a one-dimensional list so that for the i^{th} block centroid on the m^{th} branch, when each branch has n block centroid, the block centroid index is $(m+1)n + i$. Forces and torques subjected to the block centroids then are determined as two separated one-dimensional sets. In addition to the external forces and torques assigned by the designer, weight of the blocks is automatically computed as explained in the next section.

5.3 Limit state analysis

Given the data trees of the block corners on the outer and inner surfaces which determine the topology of the assemblage, geometric properties of the interlocking faces; determining the indices of the support faces; assigning the external forces and torques subjected to the block centroids; and material properties introduced in the following table, GH component *contact forces* analyse the structural feasibility of the model.

The applied limit analysis method follows the concept of concave contact model [1] in which an interlocking interface is abstracted to a number of contact points distributed on lock centrelines. The stress resultants are computed at these points by solving the equilibrium problem under the following constraints: (1) compressive constraint on the force components normal to the interface, avoiding the block separation/rocking, (2) friction constraint on the tangential internal force components along the locks, avoiding sliding along the locks and, (3) shear constraints on the tangential internal force components normal to the locks, avoiding the shear/torsional cracking of the locks.

the shear resistance at each point i on a lock centreline can be a portion of $T_0 = \tau_k sb$, through a weight p_i , so that $\sum_{i=1}^n p_i = 1$. where τ_k is the material shear strength, s is the lock thickness, and b is the lock length.

Three options are considered for the contact point distribution on the lock centerlines and weighting the shear resistant at each point as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Options for the contact point distribution of the lock centreline.

Component	Description
Contact Forces (CFs)	
Input	
Layer 0 Points (I0P)	Block corners on the outer surface
Layer 1 Points (I1P)	Block corners on the inner surface
Layer 0 UV Supports (UVS0)	Index of uv supports on the outer surface
Layer 0 WU Supports (WUS0)	Index of uw supports
Layer 0 VW Supports (VWS0)	Index of vw supports
Layer 1 UV Supports (UVS1)	Index of uv supports on the inner surface
UV0 Locks Points (UV0LP)	End points of lock centerline on uv faces on the outer surface
UV1 Locks Points (UV1LP)	End points of lock centerline on uv faces on the inner surface
WU0 Locks Points (WU0LP)	End points of lock centerline on uw faces
VW0 Locks Points (VW0LP)	End points of lock centerline on vw faces
External Forces (EF)	External force on a block centroid
External Torques (ET)	External torque on a block centroid
Friction Coefficient (FC)	
Shear Strength (ShSt)	
Density (D)	To calculate the weight of each block
Shear Resistance Option (OP)	Options for the contact point distribution of the lock centreline
Output	
UV0 Internal Forces (UV0IF)	Internal forces of uv faces on the outer surface
UV0 Points (UV0Points)	Contact points of uv faces on the outer surface
UV1 Internal Forces (UV1IF)	Internal forces of uv faces on the inner surface
UV1 Points (UV1Points)	Contact points of uv faces on the inner surface
WU0 Internal Forces (WU0IF)	Internal forces of uw faces
WU0 Points (WU0Points)	Contact points of uw faces
VW0 Internal Forces (VW0IF)	Internal forces of vw faces
VW0 Points (VW0Points)	Contact points of vw faces
Residual (Res)	

[1] Livesley, R. K. (1992). A computational model for the limit analysis of three-dimensional masonry structures. *Meccanica*, 27(3), 161-172.